

Synthesis and Characterization of Novel Potential Biologically Active 3-Alkyl(Aryl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones

Haydar Yüksek¹, Faruk Kardaş²

¹Department of Chemistry, Kafkas University, 36100 Kars, Turkey

²Erzincan University, Faculty of Education, Department of Science Education, 24002 Erzincan, Turkey

Abstract In this study, 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**4**) were synthesized from 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-amino-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**3**) with 4-methylthiobenzaldehyde. The structures of six new compounds were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR and UV spectra.

Keywords 4,5-Dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one, Schiff base, synthesis

Introduction

1,2,4-Triazole and 4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives are reported to possess a broad spectrum of biological activities [1-12]. In addition, several articles reporting the synthesis of some N-arylideneamino-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives have been published [2,6,12-16].

Scheme 1: Synthetic route of compounds **4**

In the present paper, six new potential biologically active 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**4**) were synthesized 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-amino-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**3**) with 4-methylthiobenzaldehyde (Scheme 1). Compounds **3** were prepared from the reactions of the corresponding ester ethoxycarbonylhydrazones (**2**), which were obtained by the reactions of iminoester hydrochlorides (**1**) with ethyl carbazate, with an aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate as described in the literature [17,18].

Materials and Methods

Chemical reagents and all solvents used in this study were purchased from Merck AG, Aldrich and Fluka. Melting points which were uncorrected were determined in open glass capillaries using an Electrothermal 9100 digital melting point apparatus. The IR spectra were obtained on a Mattsol 1000 FTIR spectrometer. ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide with TMS as internal standard using a Varian NMR spectrometer at 200 MHz and 50 MHz, respectively. UV absorption spectra were measured in 10 mm quartz cells between 200 and 400 nm using a Shimadzu-160A UV-VIS-NIR spectrometer. Extinction coefficients (ϵ) are expressed in L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹. Combustion analyses were performed on a LECO CHNS-932 Elemental Analyzer.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (4**).** The corresponding compound **3** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanoic acid (20 mL) and by treated 4-methylthiobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 1.5 hours and then evaporated at 50-55 °C *in vacuo*. A few recrystallizations of the residue from ethanol gave pure compounds **4**.

3-Methyl-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (4a**):** Yield 91 %, m.p. 227 °C. IR (KBr): 3167 (NH), 1708 (C=O), 1590 (C=N), 823 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring) cm⁻¹. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 2.27 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.53 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 7.35 (d, 2H, ArH, *J*=8.40 Hz), 7.76 (d, 2H, ArH, *J*=8.40 Hz), 9.67 (s, 1H, N=CH), 11.81 (s, 1H, NH). ¹³C-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 11.89 (CH₃), 15.92 (SCH₃), [127.32 (2C), 129.80 (2C), 131.60, 144.65] (ArC), 146.00 (Triazole C₃), 153.08 (N=CH), 155.11 (Triazole C₅). UV λ_{\max} (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 323 (14480), 260 (1860), 208 (10030) nm. *Anal.* Calcd for C₁₁H₁₂N₄OS: C, 53.21; H, 4.87; N, 22.56. Found: C, 53.52; H, 4.91; N, 22.47.

3-Ethyl-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (4b**):** Yield 92 %, m.p. 168 °C. IR (KBr): 3170 (NH), 1695 (C=O), 1593 (C=N), 809 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring) cm⁻¹. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 1.21 (t, 3H, CH₂CH₃, *J*=7.20 Hz), 2.52 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 2.67 (q, 2H, CH₂CH₃, *J*=7.20 Hz), 7.35 (d, 2H, ArH, *J*=8.00 Hz), 7.74 (d, 2H, ArH, *J*=8.00 Hz), 9.66 (s, 1H, N=CH), 11.80 (s, 1H, NH). ¹³C-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 11.83 (CH₂CH₃), 15.94 (SCH₃), 20.33 (CH₂CH₃), [127.33 (2C), 129.75 (2C), 131.65, 144.65] (ArC), 149.77 (Triazole C₃), 153.22 (N=CH), 155.08 (Triazole C₅). UV λ_{\max} (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 323 (23030), 260 (2120), 208 (12020) nm. *Anal.* Calcd for C₁₂H₁₄N₄OS: C, 54.94; H, 5.38; N, 21.36. Found: C, 55.17; H, 5.27; N, 21.23.

3-Benzyl-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (4c**):** Yield 95 %, m.p. 208 °C. IR (KBr): 3163 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1596 (C=N), 814 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring), 756 and 696 (monosubstituted benzenoid ring) cm⁻¹. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 2.53 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 4.05 (s, 2H, CH₂Ph), 7.32-7.37 (m, 7H, ArH), 7.72 (d, 2H, ArH, *J*=8.40 Hz), 9.63 (s, 1H, N=CH), 11.96 (s, 1H, NH). ¹³C-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 15.92 (SCH₃), 32.90 (CH₂Ph), [127.33 (2C), 128.48, 129.81 (2C), 130.21 (2C), 130.57 (2C), 131.58, 137.60, 144.73] (ArC), 147.96 (Triazole C₃), 153.07 (N=CH), 154.95 (Triazole C₅). UV λ_{\max} (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 323 (2910), 260 (3110), 208 (21240) nm. *Anal.* Calcd for C₁₇H₁₆N₄OS: C, 62.94; H, 4.97; N, 17.27. Found: C, 63.09; H, 5.05; N, 17.20.

3-(*p*-Methylbenzyl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (4d**):** Yield 93 %, m.p. 188 °C. IR (KBr): 3160 (NH), 1708 (C=O), 1592 (C=N), 825, 800 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring) cm⁻¹. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆): δ 2.24 (s, 3H, PhCH₃), 2.53 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 3.99 (s, 2H, CH₂Ph), 7.15 (d, 4H, ArH, *J*=8.00 Hz),

7.35 (d, 2H, ArH, $J=8.40$ Hz), 7.72 (d, 2H, ArH, $J=8.40$ Hz), 9.62 (s, 1H, N=CH), 11.94 (s, 1H, NH). $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 15.92 (SCH₃), 22.38 (PhCH₃), 32.50 (CH₂Ph), [127.34 (2C), 128.61 (2C), 130.43 (2C), 130.77 (2C), 131.59, 134.48, 137.47, 144.71] (ArC), 148.11 (Triazole C₃), 153.07 (N=CH), 154.91 (Triazole C₅). UV λ_{max} (ϵ , L·mol⁻¹·cm⁻¹): 323 (16600), 261 (1860), 208 (12540) nm. *Anal.* Calcd for C₁₈H₁₈N₄OS: C, 63.88; H, 5.36; N, 16.56. Found: C, 64.16; H, 5.38; N, 16.56.

3-(*p*-Chlorobenzyl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihidro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (4e): Yield 91 %, m.p. 205 °C. IR (KBr): 3110 (NH), 1706 (C=O), 1594, 1584 (C=N), 817 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring) cm⁻¹. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 2.53 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 4.05 (s, 2H, CH₂Ph), 7.34 (d, 2H, ArH, $J=8.00$ Hz), 7.36 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.71 (d, 2H, ArH, $J=8.40$ Hz), 9.63 (s, 1H, N=CH), NH (unobserved). $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 15.91 (SCH₃), 32.23 (CH₂Ph), [127.30 (2C), 129.82 (2C), 130.14 (2C), 131.51, 132.50 (2C), 133.23, 136.54, 144.77] (ArC), 147.62 (Triazole C₃), 153.05 (N=CH), 154.99 (Triazole C₅). UV λ_{max} (ϵ , L·mol⁻¹·cm⁻¹): 324 (17340), 262 (1820), 221 (14970) nm. *Anal.* Calcd for C₁₈H₁₈N₄OSCl: C, 56.90; H, 4.21; N, 15.61. Found: C, 56.96; H, 4.20; N, 15.55.

3-Phenyl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihidro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one (4f): Yield 96 %, m.p. 185 °C. IR (KBr): 3189 (NH), 1698 (C=O), 1593 (C=N), 820 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring), 771 and 693 (monosubstituted benzenoid ring) cm⁻¹. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 2.52 (s, 3H, SCH₃), 7.35 (d, 2H, ArH, $J=8.40$ Hz), 7.50-7.54 (m, 3H, ArH), 7.73 (d, 2H, ArH, $J=8.00$ Hz), 7.88-7.93 (m, 2H, ArH), 9.60 (s, 1H, N=CH), 12.38 (s, 1H, NH). $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 15.90 (SCH₃), [127.37 (2C), 128.51, 129.67 (2C), 129.98 (2C), 130.25 (2C), 131.37, 131.81, 145.07] (ArC), 146.29 (Triazole C₃), 153.21 (N=CH), 157.92 (Triazole C₅). UV λ_{max} (ϵ , L·mol⁻¹·cm⁻¹): 325 (16520), 267 (6350), 232 (12840) nm. *Anal.* Calcd for C₁₆H₁₄N₄OS: C, 61.92; H, 4.55; N, 18.05. Found: C, 61.81; H, 4.51; N, 17.87.

Results and Discussion

In this study, 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-(4-methylthiobenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihidro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**4**) were synthesized 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-amino-4,5-dihidro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**3**) with 4-methylthiobenzaldehyde. The structures of six new compounds **4** were identified by elemental analysis, IR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ and UV spectral data.

References

- [1]. Demirbas, N., Ugurluoglu, R. (2004). Synthesis and antitumor activities of some new 4-(1-naphthylideneamino)- and 4-(1-naphthylmethylamino)-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives. *Turkish Journal of Chemistry*, 28, 679–690.
- [2]. Yüksek, H., Akyıldırım, O., Yola, M.L., Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., Çelebier, M., Kart, D. (2013). Synthesis, *In vitro* antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of some new 4,5-dihidro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one Derivatives. *Archiv der Pharmazie*, 346, 470–480.
- [3]. Boy, S., Aras, A., Türkan, F., Akyıldırım, O., Beytur, M., Sedef Karaman, H., Manap, S., Yüksek, H. (2021). Synthesis, spectroscopic analysis, and *in vitro/in silico* biological studies of novel piperidine derivatives heterocyclic Schiff-Mannich base compounds. *Chem. Biodivers*, 18, e2100433.
- [4]. Amir, M., Kumar, H., Javed, S.A. (2008). Condensed bridgehead nitrogen heterocyclic system: Synthesis and pharmacological activities of 1,2,4-triazolo-[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives of ibuprofen and biphenyl-4-yloxy acetic acid. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 43(10), 2056-2066.
- [5]. Yüksek, H., Demirbas, A., İkizler, A., Johansson, C.B., Celik, C., İkizler, A. (1997). Synthesis and antibacterial activities of some 4,5-dihidro-1*H*-1,2,4- triazol-5-ones. *Arzneimittelforschung*, 47, 405–409.
- [6]. Aktas-Yokus, O., Yüksek, H., Gürsoy-Kol, O., Alpay-Karaoglu, S. (2015). Synthesis and biological evaluation of new 1,2,4-triazole derivatives with their potentiometric titrations. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 24, 2813–2824.

- [7]. Ahmad, A., Varshney, H., Rauf, A., Sherwani, A., Owais, M. (2017). Synthesis and anticancer activity of long chain substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione, 1,2,4-triazol-3-thione and 1,2,4-triazolo [3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine derivatives. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 10, S3347-S3357.
- [8]. Henen, M.A., El Bialy, S.A.A., Goda, F.E., Nasr, M.N.A., Eisa, H.M. (2012). [1,2,4]Triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline: Synthesis, antiviral, and antimicrobial activities. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 21, 2368–2378.
- [9]. Li, Z., Cao, Y., Zhan, P., Pannecouque, C., Balzarini, J., Clercq, E De. (2013). Synthesis and anti-HIV evaluation of novel 1,2,4-triazole derivatives as potential non-nucleoside HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitors. *Letters in Drug Design Discovery*, 10, 27–34.
- [10]. Boy, S., Türkan, F., Beytur, M., Aras, A., Akyıldırım, O., Sedef Karaman, H., Yüksek, H. (2021). Synthesis, design, and assessment of novel morpholine-derived Mannich bases as multifunctional agents for the potential enzyme inhibitory properties including docking study. *Bioorg. Chem.* 107, 104524.
- [11]. Eswaran, S., Adhikari, A.V., Shetty, N.S. (2009). Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel quinoline derivatives carrying 1,2,4-triazole moiety. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 44(11), 4637-4647.
- [12]. Yüksek, H., Özdemir, G., Gürsoy Kol, Ö., Manap, S., Buluttekın, S., Gökçe, S., Alkan, M. (2020). Synthesis, in vitro antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of some new 2-(3-alkyl/aryl-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl-azomethine)-phenyl benzenesulfonate derivatives. *J. Chem. Soc. Pak.* 42, 624-633.
- [13]. Gürbüz, A., Alkan, M., Manap, S., Özdemir, G., Yüksek, H. (2021). Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel 2-methoxy-6-[(3-alkyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one-4-yl)-azomethin]-phenyl benzoates with their nonaqueous medium titrations. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 10(9), 65-80.
- [14]. Yüksek, H., Bahçeci, Ş., Ocak, Z., Alkan, M., Ermiş, B., Mutlu, T., Ocak, M. (2004). Synthesis of some 4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 13, 369-372.
- [15]. Bahçeci, Ş., Yıldırım, N., Alkan, M., Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., Manap, S., Beytur, M., Yüksek, H. (2017). Investigation of antioxidant, biological and acidic properties of new 3-alkyl(aryl)-4-(3-acetoxy-4-methoxybenzylidenamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *The Pharmaceutical and Chemical Journal*, 4(4), 91-101.
- [16]. Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., Manap, S., Ozdemir, G., Beytur, M., Agdaş, E., Azap, F., Yuca, S., Alkan, M., Yüksek, H. (2020). Synthesis, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of novel 4-(2-cinnamoyloxybenzylidenamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives. *Heterocyclic letters*, 10(4), 575-587.
- [17]. İkizler, A.A., Ün, R. (1979). Reactions of ester ethoxycarbonylhydrazones with some amine type compounds. *Chim Acta Turc.* 7, 269-290.
- [18]. İkizler, A., Yüksek, H. (1993). Acetylation of 4-amino-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *Org. Prep. Proc. Int.* 25(1), 99-105.

